

Research on Ecological Restoration Mode and Policy of Mining Areas in China

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Abstract:

In order to promote the environmental restoration and management of mines in China, on the basis of comprehensive analysis of regional ecosystem stability, natural geography, climatic conditions and mine characteristics, this paper puts forward five main models of mine ecological restoration. It is clear that the ecological restoration policy ideas of China's mines are to take mining enterprises as the main body of environmental responsibility. At the same time, the government gradually improves policies and regulations, provides economic incentive policies, and formulates detailed technical

standards and operational guidelines to help them, and is committed to the ecological restoration and management of mines in China. Finally, it puts forward countermeasures and suggestions for the development of China's mine ecological environment restoration, and provides decision-making basis and governance suggestions for the mine ecological restoration work of China's and international mining industry.

Keywords: *mines, ecological restoration, remediation modes, policies.*

Introduction

While the development of mineral resources has brought rapid economic development to China, it will inevitably produce a series of serious environmental problems. The impact on the environment is mainly manifested in the destruction of land resources, mine geological disasters, soil erosion, vegetation destruction, soil and water pollution, land degradation and air pollution. At the same time, the fragmentation of the landscape will directly lead to the reduction of ecological connectivity and the reduction of biodiversity. This pollution and destruction not only endangers human health

and safety, but also hinders the construction of China's ecological civilization. Therefore, ecological and environmental management of mining areas has become an important task for green development in the mining field. Since the 1980s, China has promoted the implementation of a large number of mine ecological restoration and control projects, and has achieved certain experience and achievements, but there are still problems such as unsatisfactory ecological restoration effect and insufficient law enforcement.

This article summarizes and summarizes the development and progress of China's ecological

restoration model, laws, regulations and systems in mining areas in the past 40 years, and provides a more scientific basis for subsequent regional ecological environment improvement and social sustainable development.

Mine Ecological Restoration Model

The exploration of the ecological recovery mode of mines in foreign countries started early, and there are many successful cases worth learning from. The United States began to practice and study this area around the 1920s (Croxtton, 1928; Hu et al., 2014). The idea of ecological restoration in the United States focuses on the restoration of soil, water bodies, vegetation and other ecological elements to the original land as much as possible, that is, farmland is restored to farmland and forest restoration into forest (Wang, J. et al. 2014; He et al., 2018). Australia pays attention to recovery while mining, internalizing reclamation as part of the mining process, and emphasizes the restoration of mines to their original state as much as possible, such as the development of ecological pastures (Dole et al., 2012). Canada pays attention to local conditions and does not emphasize restoration to the original state. Open-air pits can be restored to fish ponds or puddles, and abandoned mining areas can be built into parks (Wang et al., 2013). At present, the ecological restoration of mines in Germany does not emphasize simple reclamation, but gives more consideration to the construction of ecological landscape, such as restoration into land use types such as recreational land, agricultural and forestry land and water areas (Liang et al., 2002). France is densely populated, but it attaches importance to the reclamation of open-pit mines as basic farmland (Li, 2019).

Based on the successful experience of foreign countries, China has explored a series of mine ecological restoration models based on its national conditions and adapted to local conditions. The ecological restoration of mines has changed from a single greening model to a model of land reclamation, moderate development and utilization and comprehensive improvement.

According to the state's requirements for land restoration, if conditions permit, priority should be given to agricultural land as much as possible (Hao et al., 2014). However, some mining areas have brought significant changes to the landscape, and it is not necessarily realistic to try to restore farmland or to a pre-mining state. At the same time, the contribution and impact of location advantages on subsequent gains should also be considered. Therefore, the mine recovery model is more inclined to establish diversified ecological restoration goals in reality (Li, 2006). Some scholars focus on the restoration concept on the whole ecosystem, analyze the suitability of mine ecological restoration from the comprehensive characteristics of the mine's natural conditions, geology, hydrology, topography, regional environment, etc., and determine the ecological restoration model and type of the mine (Zhou et al., 2005; Guan et al., 2017).

According to the work of former researchers, Zhang et al. (2020a) divided China's abandoned mines into 14 mine ecological restoration grounds, taking into account factors such as climate, zoning, function and location. It is proposed that if the plain basin area and the surrounding area of the city have the potential of agricultural land, priority should be given to reclamation as agricultural land. If the hilly mountainous land and desert Gobi area have natural restoration conditions, it is advisable to take natural restoration. For those that are difficult to repair into agricultural land and natural restoration, planting, aquaculture or development and construction land, ecological parks can be developed according to mining methods and site conditions in combination with manual restoration methods and site conditions. At present, most mines with complex local conditions have realized a multi-mode restoration method to dig the value of the mine and realize its ecological protection (Sun et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2017; Zhang, et al., 2020b). On the basis of integrating the research results of predecessors, Chang et al. (2022) proposes a landscape reconstruction model in three aspects: establishing a comprehensive value evaluation system for landscape reconstruction;

standardizing and optimizing the planning and design methods for landscape reconstruction; and straightening out and improving the institutional guarantee system for postmining landscape reconstruction. This management model of mine abandoned land, took the management model of abandoned mine land as a whole, and realized geological disasters and ecological environment management at the level of landscape ecosystem, so that the management of mines can be organically combined with the development of the whole region from a more macro perspective. The concept of mine governance has been improved.

At present, the goal of ecological restoration is to establish a complete ecological service system that can perform self-maintenance and operate well. On the basis of exploring different ecological restoration models, with sustainable development as the orientation, the establishment of a post-rehabilitation tracking supervision and ecological restoration benefit evaluation system will be the new trend of ecological restoration models in the future (Costanza et al., 1997; Jiang et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2022; Cheng et al., 2023). In addition, with the development of policies, capital, technology, markets and other conditions, mine tailings, tailings reservoirs, drainage sites, mining areas, etc. will be comprehensively utilized. Tailings and waste stones are made into resource products, and the site has been transformed into industrial, commercial and tourism land types. It is possible to realize the resource-based ecological restoration model and will also become a new research direction (Ma 2018;Cao et al., 2011).

Agricultural Land Model

Generally, agricultural land models are preferred in temperate plains, especially coal and non-metallic mines in plain areas. According to the different soil fertility conditions, the abundance of water resources and the stable state of the collapsed area after mining, it is sorted out into farmland, cultivated land, aquaculture land, fish ponds, farmland irrigation reservoirs, woodland, grassland, etc. to alleviate the contradiction between people and land (Wei et al., 2022). At

the same time, it can also make full use of surrounding resources to build ecological sightseeing parks, outdoor activity bases, etc. For example, Wangzhuang Coal Mine in Shanxi Province adopts a combination of three-dimensional seed and aquaculture to restore the sample land, and achieves good economic, social and ecological benefits (Wang et al., 2010).

Construction Land Model

Open-pit mining mines with relatively flat ground near cities and towns or urban-rural areas, or mined-out areas that have been backfilled, well-mined mines that have been calm in the collapse area, or metal mines with a high risk of soil heavy metal pollution, can be exchanged for construction land indicators through land transfer, bundling transfer, land reserve or reclamation to attract private capital investment for ecological and environmental management of the mining area (Shi, 2011; Li et al., 2022). It is usually required to take engineering measures for foundation treatment and ground firming. After testing by relevant departments to meet the use standards, it will be built into commercial housing, industrial parks, resort centers, conference centers, garbage treatment plants, storage land, etc., so as to alleviate the shortage of urban land resources to a certain extent.

Ecological Landscape Model

The ecological landscape model includes landscape similarity recovery model, landscape model and mine park model. With the main goal of restoration of greening, the method of natural restoration as the main body and artificial restoration as the supplement is adopted to restore the damaged land and vegetation to the zonal ecological landscape to the maximum extent. It is often used on both sides of traffic trunk lines, around rivers and lakes, nature reserves and scenic spots (Li et al., 2022).

The landscape model is mainly used near urban residential areas. It uses the terrain characteristics of mines to improve the living environment of surrounding residents while controlling the ecological environment in the form of theme squares, recreational squares and

wetland parks. Successful cases include Tangshan South Lake Ecological Park, Shanghai Chenshan Botanical Garden Mining Garden, etc.

Mine parks can be divided into three types of mining landscape, tourism development, mining landscape and tourism development (Wu et al., 2007). While managing and protecting the ecological environment, it protects mining relics and implants the new mining cultural landscape, reflecting the connotation of the landscape. Such as Hubei Huangshi National Mine Park, Zhejiang Wenling Changyu Jingtian National Mine Park, Xinjiang Cocotohai Rare Metals National Mine Park, etc.

The establishment of mining parks plays an important role in promoting the industrial transformation and sustainable development of mining cities. In 2004, the Ministry of Land and Resources issued the “Notice on the Declaration of National Mine Parks”. In 2005, the first batch of units have been qualified for mining parks. At present, a total of 89 parks have been approved in four batches. During this period, a series of research on relevant theories of landscape regeneration and cases have been carried out one after another (Wu et al., 2007; Cheng et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2007). In the continuous construction and learning, the construction level of China's mining parks has been improved, and the sustainable development of the mining economy has been promoted.

Natural Sealing Model

The natural recovery mode is suitable for mining areas with strong ecological environment sensitivity, or mining areas where natural conditions are suitable for plant growth and geological disasters and soil erosion are not serious, or remote mining areas where transportation is inconvenient and does not affect industrial and agricultural production and human settlements safety, or mining areas where engineering restoration measures are not feasible under current technical conditions. Such as tropical rainforest areas, karst desertification areas, Qinghai-Tibet Plateau forest meadow areas, subtropical mountain hilly areas, arid and semi-arid forest grassland areas and grassland

agricultural and pastoral areas with green conditions (Zhang, et al.,2020a). Generally, fence sealing is adopted to reduce human activities, without engineering intervention, and relying on the self-regulation ability of the damaged ecosystem to naturally restore the structure and function of the ecosystem. The natural breeding model has a relatively long recovery time, which has the advantage of low cost and strong sustainability of the restored ecosystem.

Ecological Environment-Oriented Development Model

In 2018, the Ministry of Ecology and Environment issued the “Guiding Opinions on Further Deepening the Reform of Delegating Administration and optimizing Services in the Field of Ecological Environment and Promoting High-quality Economic Development”. For the first time, the Urban Ecological Environment-oriented Development Model (EOD Model) was proposed, pointing out that the ecological environment-oriented development model is guided by ecological civilization and can be sustainable. The goal of continuous development is to promote the effective integration of ecological environmental governance projects with strong public welfare and poor profitability and related industries with good returns on the basis of ecological protection and environmental governance, supported by the operation of characteristics of characteristic industries, and regional comprehensive regional comprehensive development as the carrier. The overall promotion, integrated implementation, and the organization and implementation of projects that internalize the economic value brought by ecological and environmental governance. Through this development model, the integrated development of government, enterprises and communities will be gradually promoted. According to “Notice on Recommending the Pilot Project of Ecological Environment-oriented Development Model”, “Notice on Agreeing to the Pilot Project of Ecological Environment-oriented Development (EOD) Model” and “Notice on Agreeing to the Pilot of the Second Batch of Ecological Environment-

oriented Development (EOD) Model”, 94 projects have been selected in the list of projects, among which the more representative specific cases include the ecological comprehensive management improvement project of Fenghuang Greenway Area in Zaozhuang City, Shandong Province, the EOD project of comprehensive ecological environment management in Xiangshan area of Ma'anshan City, and the construction and comprehensive development and utilization of the water ecological environment of Xiaoshou International New City in Yunnan Middle New Area, Yunnan Province. EOD project and revitalization and development of Bazhong Old Revolutionary Area and Ba River Governance EOD Project, etc.

Policy Research

The Stage Dominated by Reclamation

The ecological restoration stage of mines, which focuses on reclamation, began in the 1960s. Since then, although the mine restoration work has been gradually carried out, it was not until the promulgation of “Regulations on Land Reclamation” in 1989 that it marked that the ecological restoration of mines in China has entered a period of law and initially formed a certain scale (Hu, 2019). The ecological restoration content of the reclamation stage mainly includes slope restoration, ecological reclamation, acid wastewater, acid wastewater treatment, acid wastewater soil texture improvement, soil heavy metal treatment, greening, etc. It is a comprehensive and systematic project. Therefore, the ecological restoration of mines in China is jointly managed by multiple departments. Among them, the land department is mainly responsible for mine reclamation, and the environmental protection department is responsible for the post-implementation effect and water and soil pollution (Zhai, 2022). The provisions on legal responsibilities for ecological restoration are scattered in environmental protection laws and regulations and relevant normative documents. Relevant laws and regulations such as the “Land Reclamation Regulations”, “Environmental

Protection Law”, “Yangtze River Protection Law”, “Water Pollution Prevention and Control Law”, “Mineral Resources Law”, “Coal Law”, “Water and Soil Conservation Law” and other relevant laws and regulations clearly stipulate that the development and utilization of mineral resources should pay attention to environmental protection, and the mine ecological environment should be protected by means of sewage fees and ecological environment compensation fees, mineral resources compensation fees and resource taxes, and the mine environmental management and restoration deposit system.

The Stage of Regional Geological Environmental Protection Based on Reclamation

Improvement of laws and regulations

In 2006, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Land and Resources and the State Administration of Environmental Protection jointly issued “Guiding Opinions of the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Land and Resources and the State Administration of Environmental Protection on the Gradually Establishing Responsibility Mechanism for Mine Environmental Governance and Ecological Restoration”, which promoted the administrative departments of finance, land and resources and environmental protection at all levels to attach great importance to the establishment of mine environmental governance. The work of the ecological restoration responsibility mechanism is combined with geological environmental protection on the basis of reclamation, and constantly improve the ecological restoration system of the mine.

A series of policy and regulatory documents have been issued, such as “Provisions on Land Reclamation”, “Land Administration Law of the People's Republic of China”, “Coal Law of the People's Republic of China” and other laws and regulations, which have played a certain role in the reclamation work. At the same time, with the continuous improvement of policies and regulations, the ecological restoration of mining areas will be more standardized, systematic and scientific.

For example, the “Standards for the Preparation of Environmental Protection and Comprehensive Management Plans in Mines” were promulgated in 2007, the “Regulations on the Geological Environmental Protection of Mines” were promulgated and implemented in 2009. In 2011, State Council promulgated and implemented “Regulations on Land Reclamation”, which requires reclamation while mining in construction and production mines. In the same year, the “Standards for the Preparation of Mine Geological Environmental Protection and Restoration Management Plan” was issued and implemented. In 2013, “Regulations for the Preparation of Land Reclamation Schemes” were issued, and in 2014, “Regulations for Land Reclamation Acceptance for Production Projects” were implemented. In the same year, “Technical Standards for Mine Ecological Environmental Protection and Restoration and Management (Trial)” were issued. In 2016, “Guiding Opinions on Strengthening the Restoration and Comprehensive Management of Mine Geological Environment” was issued. So far, the land reclamation system has been further improved while carrying out geological environment management.

In 2017, the Ministry of Land and Resources released the “National Land Remediation Plan (2016-2020)”, in which local governments paid attention to land reclamation and land ecological improvement. During this period, all provinces have successively issued a series of local regulations on mine restoration measures and regulations, and have experienced the evolution from the deposit of mine land reclamation expenses, deposit to the fund system, so as to reduce the operating costs of mining enterprises and stimulate the enthusiasm of enterprises to use and manage the fund independently. “National Major Projects for the Protection and Restoration of Important Ecosystems (2021-2035)”, released in 2020, proposes to scientifically carry out and strengthen the ecological restoration of mining areas in key national ecological functional areas, reshape topography and landforms, rebuild vegetation in mining areas, and restore mine ecology. It can be

seen that the ecological restoration of mining areas is still an important measure to promote the construction of ecological civilization and ensure national ecological security in the future.

In 2022, Jiangxi Province took the lead in promulgating the provincial local regulations on mine ecological restoration “Regulations on Ecological Restoration and Utilization of Mines in Jiangxi Province”, which provides an effective rule of law solution for mine ecological restoration, and is a specific practice that leads and promotes mine restoration with legislative decisions.

China's existing policy practice of mine environmental governance and restoration is transitioning from command control mode to policy incentive mode to solve the problems of historical arrears, many practical contradictions and insufficient capital investment in mine ecological restoration. Specific measures include improving financial support policies and ecological compensation systems, establishing special funds, providing preferential tax policies, such as reduction and exemption of environmental protection tax, corporate income tax and value-added tax, promulgation of the Regulations on Ecological Protection Compensation, etc (Fan et al., 2024). These measures effectively lower the economic threshold for enterprises to participate in ecological restoration and encourage more enterprises to actively participate in ecological restoration in mining areas. Since the issuance of “Opinions of the Ministry of Natural Resources on Exploring the Use of Market-based Methods to Promote Ecological Restoration in Mines” and “Opinions on Establishing an Incentive Mechanism to Accelerate the Ecological Restoration of Mines”, mining enterprises, as the main body of ecological environmental damage, are gradually assuming their due responsibilities, trying to internalize the social costs caused by mineral development, gradually establishing an economic mechanism for enterprises to protect the environment, and forming environmental management rules suitable for the development of mineral resources under the conditions of market economy (Pang et al., 2024). We will clearly encourage the comprehensive restoration

and utilization of mine land, encourage the production and construction of mine-side mining and border restoration, and give mine restoration enterprises a certain right to use and manage the construction land, solve the bottlenecks of insufficient investment, and accelerate the ecological restoration of mines.

Formulation of technical standards and guidelines

In the ecological restoration of the mining area, the formulation of detailed technical standards and operating guidelines can ensure the scientificity, standardization and effectiveness of the restoration work. In 2008, "National Mineral Resources Plan (2008-2015)" issued by the former Ministry of Land and Resources clearly stated that "by 2020, the green mine pattern will be basically established". So far, according to the environmental protection requirements of the national green mine construction evaluation index, the ecological restoration and construction of mines has been organically integrated with the implementation of environmental factor quality standards, pollution prevention and control standards and pollutant discharge standards (Duan et al., 2024). In order to improve work efficiency and reduce the burden on mining enterprises, the Ministry of Land and Resources in 2016 issued "Guidelines for the Preparation of Mine Geological Environmental Protection and Land Reclamation Plan". In April 2018, the Ministry of Natural Resources announced the construction norms for green mines in nine industries: non-metallic, chemical industry, gold, coal, sand and gravel, petroleum, cement limestone, metallurgy and non-ferrous metallurgy industries. Some local governments have successively formulated and issued provincial construction standards and development requirements (Si et al., 2020; Wang, 2018). In 2022, "Technical Specification for Ecological Restoration in Mines" was implemented. This standard is the first time nationwide to formulate an industry standard for ecological restoration in mines. It is an important technical guarantee for China to improve the ecological environment quality of mines from quantity to qualitative change. Subsequently, a series of local standards have also been approved

and issued one after another, providing a strong guarantee for the comprehensive restoration of the ecological environment in mining areas. However, in general, there are too few standards and norms on production technology and safety management, which need to be further strengthened (Cai et al., 2024).

Conclusion

In summary, based on the exploration and practice of China's existing mine ecological restoration model and policy, the formulation of future policies should advocate considering the land use after closure from the early planning stage of the mine, and incorporate it as part of the dynamic and developing closure plan during the operation of the mine, including regulatory requirements, community opinions, economic factors and later management needs. The future research direction should focus on developing efficient and low-cost restoration technologies to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of ecological restoration in mining areas. Strengthen the monitoring and evaluation of the long-term effect of the restoration project to ensure the continuous and stable operation of the restored ecosystem. The important direction of ecological restoration research in the future is to explore and promote the restoration mode that adapts to the characteristics of different mining areas, form a universally applicable repair mode library to provide detailed technical guidelines and successful cases, and ensure the effective application of the repair mode library in actual repair work through technical training, policy support and public participation. We will further strengthen international experience exchange and cooperation, share advanced restoration technology and management experience, and jointly meet the global challenges of ecological restoration in mining areas.

In a word, the research and practice of ecological restoration in mining areas is a complex and systematic project that requires multiple collaboration and continuous investment. The future development direction will pay more attention to science, technology and innovation,

policy support and social participation, and strive to achieve the comprehensive restoration and sustainable development of the mining environment.

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